

John Smith recommended the use of lemon juice as a treatment for scurvy (1626)

by Harri Hemilä

James Lind is often credited with discovering or proving that citrus fruits are effective in preventing and treating scurvy. However, reports highlighting the benefits of oranges appeared more than two centuries before Lind's (1753) treatise. Oranges were already indicated for scurvy in accounts from Vasco da Gama's first voyage,¹ and similar suggestions were recorded by Ronsseus,² Hawkins,³ Pyrrard,⁴ Woodall,⁵ Winthrop⁶ and many others before Lind's treatise.⁷ In his instructions to seamen, John Smith suggested juice of lemons in 1626. The relevant passage from his text is reproduced in this document.

The extracted text section was cited in:

Tickner FJ, Medvei VC. Scurvy and the health of European crews in the Indian Ocean in the seventeenth century. *Med Hist.* 1958;2(1):36-46. [p.43]
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/13515823>

Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

This text is available at:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623986>
2026-2-12

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<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Hemilä.

1 Scurvy during *Vasco da Gama's* first voyage (1497-1499).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>

2 Description of scurvy by Ronsseus (1564).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093314>

3 Scurvy during *Richard Hawkins's* voyage (1593).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001137>

4 *François Pyrrard's* description of scurvy during a sea voyage (1602-1603).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18415628>

5 Description of scurvy symptoms by *John Woodall* (1617).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10651214>

6 *John Winthrop* describes the treatment of scurvy with lemon juice (1631)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18619215>

7 Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment.

Nutr Rev. 2009;67(6):315-32. [p.317-318]

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/19519673>

John Smith (c. 1579 – 21 June 1631), biographies

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Smith_\(explorer\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Smith_(explorer))

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1923876>

<https://doi.org/10.2307/2209364>

<https://doi.org/10.2307/1918849>

<https://www.jstor.org/stable/4245921>

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/3130>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=inu.30000055032464&seq=9>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.35112104456571&seq=11>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=mdp.39015027057671&seq=3>

Section describing juice of lemons for scurvy:

1626, p.39

<https://quod.lib.umich.edu/e/eebo/A12455.0001.001>

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1475-1640_an-accidence-or-the-path_smith-john-governor-of_1626/page/38/mode/2up

1636, p.58

https://archive.org/details/bim_early-english-books-1641-1700_an-accidence-or-the-path_smith-john-governor-of_1636/page/n67/mode/2up

1626, p.39:

... A Commaunder at sea
should do well to thinke the contrary,
and prouide for himselfe and company
in like manner; also seriously to consi-
der what will be his charge, to furnish
himselfe at sea, with bedding, linnen,
armes and apparell; how to keepe his
table aboard, his expences on shore,
and his petty tally, which is a compe-
tent proportion according to your
number, of these particulars following.

Fine wheat flower, close and well
packed, *Rise, Currands, Sugar, Prunes,*
Cinamon, Ginger, Pepper, Cloues,
Greene-ginger, Oyle, Butter, Olde Cheese,
or Holland, Wine vinegar, Canary Sacke,
Aqua vitae, the best Wines, the best Waters,
the iuyce of Lemons for the Scuruey,
white Bisket, Oate-meale, Gammons of Ba-
ron, dried neates tongues, Rosted Beefe,
packed vp in vineger.